

Individual Researchers' Research Productivity: A Comparative Analysis of Counting Methods

Éric Archambault,¹ Vincent Larivière²

¹ eric.archambault@science-metrix.com
Science-Metrix and CIRST, Université du Québec à Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada

² lariviere.vincent@uqam.ca
Observatoire des sciences et des technologies, Université du Québec à Montréal, Montréal, Québec, Canada

Introduction

Productivity can be studied at different scales (e.g., country, organisation, author). The present work examines productivity at the researcher level, with the financial support received by researchers representing input and researchers' papers representing output. Regardless of the scale at which productivity is examined, science must be considered a collective endeavour, particularly since there is a growing trend towards more collaboration in nearly every field. Importantly though, very distinct collaboration practices exist across fields of research. For instance, over 90% of the papers in the natural sciences and engineering (NSE) are written in collaboration (more than one author), whereas this proportion is 60% in the social sciences and 10% in the humanities (Larivière, Gingras and Archambault, 2006). Whether one uses fractional or whole counts can be expected to yield hugely different productivity measures (Lindsey, 1980; Egghe, Rousseau, and Van Hooydonk, 2000; Gauffriau, M. et al., 2008). This paper examines how fractional versus whole-paper counting affects the measurement of researchers' performance in the social sciences and the humanities (SSH) versus in the NSE.

Method

This paper uses a very large dataset comprising funding, publication and citation data of all professors and university-based researchers (hereafter "researchers") in the Canadian province of Quebec over the 2000–2007 period (1999–2006 for funding). To compile this dataset, lists of researchers (n=13,479) were obtained from Quebec's Ministère du développement économique, de l'innovation et de l'exportation, and its three research councils. Bibliometric indicators in this paper were calculated using Thomson Reuters' Web of Science database for the 2000–2007 period (n=62,026 papers). Research funding comes from the SIRU database. Statistics on output per researcher were computed for researchers with at least one paper, while those on output per research dollar were computed for researchers with at least one paper and one dollar of financial support. This was deemed necessary so that the fact that researchers in the SSH often prefer books to peer-reviewed journals could be taken into account (Larivière et al., 2006).

Results

Table 1 shows that when full-paper counting is used, researchers in the basic medical sciences are the most productive, followed closely by natural scientists. Health sciences and engineering researchers follow at a certain distance, while those in the humanities and various social sciences trail noticeably. However, fractional counting evens things out in a drastic manner: productivity falls to one paper every other year,

on average, in the natural sciences (i.e., 4.1 papers over the eight-year period). Researchers in the SSH were half as productive, i.e., one full-paper equivalent every four years. Education researchers did not produce the equivalent of a full paper during the eight year period.

Table 1. Difference in measured productivity, full and fractional counting, 2000–2007

Field	Full counting	Fractional counting	Ratio (Full/Fractional)
Natural Sciences	17,4	4,1	4,2
Engineering	13,2	3,7	3,6
Basic Medical Sciences	20,3	3,3	6,3
Health Sciences	14,6	2,3	6,5
Humanities	2,5	2,1	1,2
Social Sciences	6,9	2,1	3,4
Business & Management	4,5	1,4	3,1
Non-Health Professional	4,4	1,4	3,1
Education	2,3	0,6	3,6

If one looks at productivity per research dollar, the results are even more striking: whereas papers in the basic medical sciences cost in excess of \$475,000 on average, researchers in the humanities produced papers for less than \$75,000 each. As previously noted, SSH researchers usually prefer to publish books instead of papers. Moreover, Thomson Reuters seriously underestimates the production of works in languages other than English, which are common in the SSH (Archambault et al., 2006). This means that productivity in the SSH is underestimated and the cost per publication in the SSH is likely substantially lower in reality.

Figure 1. Cost per paper, fractional and full counting, by discipline, 2000–2007

References

- Archambault, É. et al. 2006. Benchmarking scientific output in the social sciences and humanities: The limits of existing databases, *Scientometrics* 68: 329-342.
- Egghe, L., Rousseau, R., and Van Hooydonk, G. (2000). Methods for accrediting publications to authors or countries: Consequences for evaluation studies. *JASIST* 51: 145-157.
- Gauffriau, M., et al. (2008). Methods for accrediting publications to authors or countries: Consequences for evaluation studies. *Scientometrics* 77: 147-176.

- Larivière, V. et al. (2006) The place of serials in referencing practices: Comparing natural sciences and engineering with social sciences and humanities. *JASIST* 57: 997-1004.
- Larivière, V., Gingras, Y. and Archambault, É. (2006) Canadian collaboration networks: A comparative analysis of the natural sciences, social sciences and the humanities. *Scientometrics* 68: 519-533.
- Lindsey, D. (1980). Production and citation measures in the sociology of science: the problem of multiple authorship. *Social Studies of Science* 10: 145-162.

Science-Metrix

Observatoire
des sciences et des
technologies

Measuring SSH and NSE Scientific Production Using Full-Paper and Fractional Counting

Background (1)

- Distributions of researchers' productivity and citations have been studied fairly extensively by early information scientists (e.g. Cole and Eales, 1917; Lotka, 1926)
- It has been shown time and again that the distribution of scientific output is non-linear, it is highly skewed and has long-tail characteristics and, hence, very concentrated
- Citation per researchers are even more concentrated
- Explanations of these extreme differences in scientists' performances are generally of two types (Cole and Cole, 1973).
- The "sacred spark" hypothesis says that there are predetermined differences in the scientists' ability and motivation to perform creative scientific research.
- The alternative hypothesis is that of "accumulative advantages" – which draws on Merton' Matthew effect (Merton, 1973).

Background (2)

- Though scientists certainly differ and though there are certainly accumulative advantage, as well as very different social predispositions to have different level of productivity, structural factors are certainly very important too.
- In particular, the propensity to collaborate must have a very important different effect on the measured productivity of researchers
- We know that collaboration is increasingly encouraged as it is perceived as increasing the quality of research and interdisciplinarity is meant to help larger and more complex problems
- However, the propensity to collaborate varies among fields – natural scientists collaborate much more than social scientists and scholars in the humanities largely work – and publish – alone.

Background (3)

- For instance, over 90% of the papers in the natural sciences and engineering (NSE) are written in collaboration (that is, with more than one author), whereas this proportion is 60% in the social sciences and 10% in the humanities (Larivière, Gingras and Archambault, 2006).
- If one counts papers as fractional or whole counts, these differences can be expected to have hugely different effects on the measured productivity (Lindsey, 1980; Egghe, Rousseau, and Van Hooydonk, 2000; Gauffriau, M. et al., 2008).
- One can expect that difference in productivity between natural scientists and social scientists to become somewhat narrower
- However, we don't know the precise extent of the differences that can be observed in productivity

Background (4)

- Productivity can be studied at different scales (e.g., country, organisation, author) and using various measures, including number of pages written and number of papers (Serenko, 2010)
- This presentation concentrates on the **individual level**
- We will examine the effect of using full-paper and fractional counting techniques on **scientific impact** as a function of production (citations/papers), overall **cost per paper**, and **productivity** in various disciplines (papers per researchers; dollars per paper) and **concentration** (GINI coefficient).

Methods (list of researchers)

- In order to compile data at the level of individuals, the list of all of Quebec university researchers and professors (N=13,744) provided by Quebec' Government was used.
- Coming from four different sources, this list included several double counts which were carefully eliminated. In addition to include the names (family name and given name) of researchers, this list also included their university and department, which proved very helpful for the reconstitution of researchers' publication files.
- Each professor and university-affiliated researcher in Quebec was categorized into one of 9 disciplinary category that cover all fields of university research, which were adapted from the Classification of instructional programs (CIP).

Disciplinary classification of researchers

Basic Medical Sciences

- Surgical Specialties
- Medical Specialties
- Laboratory Medicine
- General Medicine

Business & Management

Education

Engineering

- Mechanical & Industrial Engineering
- Other Engineering
- Electrical & Computer Engineering
- Civil Engineering
- Chemical Engineering

Health Sciences

- Public Health & Health Administration
- Kinesiology / Physical Education
- Rehabilitation Therapy
- Nursing
- Dentistry
- Other Health Sciences

Humanities

- History
- Fine & Performing Arts
- Philosophy
- French/English
- Religious Studies & Vocations
- Foreign Languages Literature, Linguistics & Area Studies

Non-Health Professional

- Planning & Architecture
- Media & Communication Studies
- Social Work
- Library & Information Sciences
- Law & Legal Studies

Natural Sciences

- Resource Management & Forestry
- Agricultural & Food Sciences
- Earth & Ocean Sciences
- Computer & Information Science
- Biology & Botany
- Mathematics
- Physics & Astronomy
- Chemistry

Social Sciences

- Other Social Sciences & Humanities
- Political Science
- Economics
- Psychology
- Geography
- Anthropology, Archaeology & Sociology

Relationship between papers and citations (1)

Relationship between papers and citations (2)

Relationship between papers and cost (1)

Relationship between papers and cost (2)

Difference in concentration

Gini Coefficient

Papers

Citations

	Papers			Citations		
	Full Count	Fractional Count	Greater Concentration	Full Count	Fractional Count	Greater Concentration
Humanities	0.40	0.41	Fraction	0.86	0.82	Full
Non-Health Professional	0.60	0.53	Full	0.85	0.78	Full
Social Sciences	0.57	0.52	Full	0.80	0.78	Full
Education	0.45	0.48	Fraction	0.77	0.77	Full
Health Sciences	0.59	0.56	Full	0.74	0.71	Full
Business & Management	0.54	0.53	Full	0.73	0.72	Full
Engineering	0.54	0.54	Fraction	0.73	0.72	Full
Natural Sciences	0.54	0.51	Full	0.72	0.69	Full
Basic Medical Sciences	0.55	0.57	Fraction	0.68	0.70	Fraction
All Papers	0.59	0.56	Full	0.77	0.75	Full

Difference in productivity – paper per researcher (2000-2007)

Field	Full counting	Fractional counting	Ratio (Full/Fractional)
Natural Sciences	17.4	4.1	4.2
Engineering	13.2	3.7	3.6
Basic Medical Sciences	20.3	3.3	6.3
Health Sciences	14.6	2.3	6.5
Humanities	2.5	2.1	1.2
Social Sciences	6.9	2.1	3.4
Business & Management	4.5	1.4	3.1
Non-Health Professional	4.4	1.4	3.1
Education	2.3	0.6	3.6

Cost per paper full vs. fraction count

A. Full Counting

B. Fractional Counting

Conclusion

- This research presents strong evidence in support of cumulative advantage (Matthew & ratchet effects)
 - Researchers who publish are more cited than if citation was in a linear relation to publication
 - Relationship may kick-in around 10 fractionally counted paper
- There seem to be decreasing return to scale in research – the larger the R&D revenues the less they publish relatively

Conclusion

- Fractional counting does not lead to vastly different results when measuring research impact but measurements show slightly greater concentration levels with full paper counting
- As expected, productivity as measured in papers per researcher reveals that fractional counting presents a more level field picture of output in various research area than full paper counting
- The capital intensity of PEER REVIEWED papers in the humanities is perhaps even greater than one would have thought (using fractional counting) - whereas basic medical sciences papers cost in excess of \$475,000 per paper, researchers in the humanities produced papers for less than \$75,000 each.

Contact:

Eric Archambault, D.Phil.

President, [Science-Metrix](#)

E-mail: eric.archambault@science-metrix.com

www.science-metrix.com

